

Assessing the Competitiveness of Universities by Different Methods

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Abstract: This article talks about the methodology of evaluating the competitiveness of higher education institutions, the sequence of using this methodology and the analysis. The purpose of the article is to study the competitiveness of higher education in the context of ensuring the sustainable development of the state. The methodological basis of this article is a set of such methods as system analysis, logical generalization, analysis and synthesis, statistical analysis, abstract-logical, induction and deduction, graphic and others.

Keywords: competitiveness, integration of production and education, career.

In the stable economic development of the country, the level of literacy of the population and their state of education are of great importance. In particular, the compliance of higher education with modern trends, the state of the quality of education directly affects the potential of the main labor resources of the country. In order to implement these tasks, the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" was adopted. Paragraph 1 of this decree includes at least 10 higher education institutions in the republic in the list of higher education institutions in the first 1,000 places in the ranking of internationally recognized organizations (Quacquarelli Symonds World University Rankings, Times Higher Education or Academic Ranking of World Universities), including the National University of Uzbekistan. University and Samarkand State University in the list of the first 500 higher education institutions, as well as raising the content of higher education to a new level in terms of quality, establishing a system of training highly qualified personnel who can make a worthy contribution to the stable development of the social sphere and economic sectors, and who can find their place in the labor market. tasks were defined.

Due to the lack of a clear definition of competition at higher education market, insufficient scientific definitions of competitiveness of basic and additional educational services and products are available. Therefore it is necessary to modernize the theoretical basis of the marketing management of competitiveness of a comparative educational organization¹.

The creation of a competitive environment in the higher education system creates the need for a reasonable and correct assessment of the competitiveness of each higher education institution. In the course of our scientific research, we analyzed the competitiveness of state

¹ A.A. Voronov, V.E. Garkovenko, A.M. Safonov, S.N. Kosnikov. Higher Education Competitiveness: Definition, Assessment and Ways of Growth. European Research Studies Journal Volume XXI, Special Issue 1, 2018. pp. 525-534

higher education institutions in the Bukhara region and conducted analyzes according to the activity, position and income of their graduates in the economic sector. Our online survey was as follows:

- Specify the name of the higher education institution you graduated from
- Your field of study at the institution of higher education
- Are you working in the field you graduated from the higher education institution?
- Your place in management
- How much is your monthly income? (if it's not a secret, in million soums)
- Scope of your position (number of employees under your control)
- How do you rate the competitiveness of the higher education institution you graduated from in the Bukhara region? (in the range from 1 to 100 points)
- How do you evaluate the training of the pedagogues of the higher educational institution where you studied?
- How important were the subjects taught at the higher educational institution you graduated from in your professional development?
- Did you have the opportunity to do internships and internships in enterprises and organizations at the higher educational institution you graduated from?
- How often were events held with the participation of production and service industry specialists in the higher education institutions you graduated from?
- How do you rate the practical support of the management of the higher education institution you graduated from (consultations on employment, career development)?
- Have you participated in scientific research or projects during your studies?
- How long did it take you to find a job after graduation?
- How do you get paid now compared to what you expected?
- How do you rate the environment at the university/institute you graduated from (friendly, supportive)?
- Would you recommend the university/institute you graduated from to future applicants?
- What changes or improvements would you suggest to increase the competitiveness of your university?

This questionnaire will be conducted among at least 900 respondents and the results will be econometrically analyzed using the Stata program. The regression equation is constructed and the Gauss-Markov condition is checked. Based on the results of the research, specific proposals are developed, forecasts are made, and measures are taken to introduce them to higher education institutions.

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